

Assessment Tools for English 6 Through Aralinks at St. Bridget College, Batangas City

Gina Z. Medrano¹

1 – Golden Gate Colleges, Batangas
medranogina27@gmail.com

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Abstract

This study examined the assessment tools used in teaching English 6 through Aralinks at St. Bridget College, Batangas City. It aimed to determine how effective and appropriate these digital tools are in assessing students' English skills, particularly in reading, writing, grammar, vocabulary, and communication. A mixed-methods approach was employed, involving surveys, interviews, classroom observations, and the analysis of students' academic outputs. Participants included English 6 teachers and students, as well as relevant academic records.

The results showed that Aralinks-based assessment tools, such as online quizzes, performance tasks, peer-review activities, and rubric-based assessments, helped increase student engagement and allowed teachers to give timely and meaningful feedback. These tools also supported varied teaching strategies that addressed different learning needs. Despite these benefits, the study identified challenges related to limited access to technology, varying levels of students' digital skills, and the need for further teacher training.

Overall, the study found that Aralinks has strong potential to improve assessment practices in English 6 when used thoughtfully and consistently. To maximize its effectiveness, the study recommends continuous teacher development, regular evaluation of assessment tools, and improved access to digital resources for students. The findings offer valuable insights for enhancing digital assessment practices in basic education

Keywords: *assessment tools, Aralinks, digital resources, teaching strategies, learning management system*

Introduction

Context and Rationale

Efficient assessment methodologies in the current Philippine basic education are significant for assuring that students achieve the competencies specified by the Department of Education (DepEd) K-12 and MATATAG Curriculum. The use of Learning Management Systems (LMS) and digital platforms to help in teaching, learning and assessment during the pandemic and until now.

One of the digital platforms is the Aralinks CLE (Collaborative Learning Environment) by Phoenix Aralinks. It is used as a digital tool for lessons, tests, making the student more interested, tracking student's activities and grading. In elementary schools like St. Bridget College using these online platforms gives teachers new way to assess student learning that are timely, meaningful and real.

In St. Bridget College, Batangas City this study examines Grade 6 English where the Aralinks CLE is integrated into the assessment framework and learning delivery. The assessment tools used in English 6 course through Aralinks goal is to look of how they are made, how they are used and how they help students learn meaningfully and teacher can easily give feedback. Given the growing reliance on digital assessments, it is timely and pertinent to comprehend the nature of these tools, their alignment with curriculum objectives, and their impact on pedagogical practices.

This study aims to enhance the understanding of formative and summative assessment in a blended learning environment within a Philippine elementary school context by examining assessment tools (quizzes, long tests, performance tasks, assignments) facilitated through Aralinks. The results may assist educators, school administrators, and policymakers in identifying optimal strategies for utilizing LMS-based assessment tools to improve English language acquisition, especially in upper elementary levels.

Brief Review of Literature

This part of the study presents the concepts and essential information about assessment tools for English 6 through aralinks at St. Bridget College. It includes the respondent's knowledge on how to use aralinks on English assessment in terms of technological integration, student engagement and learning outcomes. The study also examines to what extent does integrating aralinks in English instruction that improve skills like grammar, vocabulary and fluency. This study also evaluates the effectiveness of Aralinks in the students' learning outcomes through formative and quarterly test performance. Finally, the study aims to assess the challenges that are encountered by the learners in utilizing the learning management system.

Phoenix Publishing House, Inc. develops the Aralinks that is a K-12 learning management system (LMS) that is designed to assist in lesson delivery, assessment, gamification, tracking student progress, grading and interactive eBooks. Some schools with the partnership of

Phoenix Publishing House, Inc. report that Aralinks was used to plan, create and carry out lessons, activities, assessment and evaluation in digital environment.

Utilizing Aralinks in Grade 6 English class at St. Bridget College could allow learners engage more on dynamic assessments like online quizzes, interactive tasks and instant feedback rather than purely traditional paper-based tests. On the other hand, literature states that success requires getting the appropriate teacher training, latest content or strategies, the proper tools like connectivity and devices and a combination of traditional as well as digital forms.

The objective of assessment in English is to keep track of the way learners are learning, provide them with feedback, support educators prepare lessons, activities and help students develop their language skills (reading, writing, speaking and listening). There are variety of assessment tools. A well-designed assessment tool is important because it corresponds with the objective of the curriculum, the goals of language proficiency and both formative and summative purposes. The tools for grade 6 English need to assess their knowledge in grammar, vocabulary as well as the skills in reading comprehension, writing structure and speaking with others.

Naldoza (2024) conducted a study about the impact of ICT integration, particularly employing the Aralinks Learning Management System (LMS) on the academic performance of Grade 9 biology students. In his study two classes were selected one as the experimental group with ICT integration while the other group uses traditional instruction. Based on the findings, exploring factors contributing to the improvement of alternative strategies for enhancing performance. Teacher training and competence are crucial factors in utilizing the effectiveness of ICT integration. Overall, this study contributes to the ongoing discourse on leveraging ICT for educational advancement and highlights avenues for further exploration to optimize its benefits in teaching and learning contexts.

According to Koutska (2023), during the COVID-19 pandemic distance learning has gone through many changes. Technology has helped education to continue to keep improving the quality of teaching and learning. In his study the respondents use devices as virtual online tools and increased the collaborative, communicative and interactive synchronous tools. Students' homework or activities are sent through e-mail or in different Learning Management System with no possibility of physical contacts. Teachers also discovered and studied different ways to make teaching and learning more interactive in the new normal. In his study he emphasizes that the pandemic increases the variety of educational software and tools that help teaching community be more productive in the new normal.

In a related study, Pino and Merin (2021) educators hold multiple challenges on top of their responsibilities being one of the greatly affected sectors in the current global crisis. Their study came upon challenges that the educators encountered like distance learning and dealing with stakeholders. These challenges made the educators vulnerable in times of pandemic. Despite these challenges, educators learn how to bear up against difficulties and adapt through changes. Accepting challenges and rising above it is useful and helpful in addressing the needs of educators.

Nieves et al. (2025) found that Artificial Intelligence (AI) is transforming teaching and learning specifically assessment practices, administrative efficiency and preparation for future careers. In their study they examine the experiences, coping mechanism and insights of Filipino teachers in using AI driven strategies to enhance student performance. The result of their study highlights the challenges like poor internet connectivity, technological issues and inconsistent digital access. They also emphasize the resilience and creativity of teachers that emphasizes how important professional development and collaboration in achieving inclusive learning environment.

According to Albatti (2023) his study indicated that stating the Intended learning outcomes and planning are useful for practical English language teaching and learning. His findings suggest adopting specific instructional strategies such as graphic organizers that record what students know, what they have learned and what they have learned that significantly improves communicating intended learning outcomes to students. The study recommends further study of strategies that improve students' engagement in the assessment process. It also provides an overview of learning motivation theories and highlights their direct bearing on achieving learning outcomes during the learning process.

Al-khresheh and Orak (2021) explored the perspective held by English teachers regarding the role of teaching grammar in classrooms. The findings revealed that positive and constructive attitude regarding the importance of grammar instruction that good grammatical skills enabled the faster acquisition of proficiency in the language. Comprehensive discussion of the pedagogical implications and recommendations are needed.

In addition, Reynolds and Kao (2019) study indicated that pedagogical practices providing focused grammatical instruction with direct focused feedback are more beneficial to L2 writers than only providing error connection. Grammar feedback provided in-time feedback during game play provides opportunities to engage awareness-raising language related. Game play combined with written corrective feedback resulted in stronger retention of grammatical knowledge compared to learners that received teacher instruction combined with written corrective feedback.

August et al. (2020) explored in their study the efficacy of an intervention designed to improve second-grade English learners' knowledge of challenging English vocabulary. The authors assessed whether the intervention had a differential effect on content words that differ on two attributes and whether the effects lasted across time. Their study helps validate a multifaceted approach to vocabulary intervention and research.

This study of Sadeghi et al. (2022) examined and compare the impact of gamified and non-gamified instruction on the vocabulary development and motivation of students enrolled in an English language preparatory program. The findings revealed that the implementation of gamified instruction positively influenced student motivation. The students perceived gamified instruction as an efficient way to learn and practice vocabulary. The gathered findings provide pedagogical implications and suggestions for implementing gamified instruction in language classrooms.

Tavakoli, Kendon and Ziomek (2023), investigated how oral fluency is assessed across different levels of proficiency in the test of English for Educational Purposes. The results proposed changes that can help refine the fluency rating descriptions and training materials in the TEEP.

Moreover, McCallum and Milner (2020) studied the implementation of formative e-assessments in courses taken by students. Their central aim is to measure the effectiveness of the formative e-assessments with reference to the student voice and staff reflections. The findings allowed academics to reflect on the benefits of adopting formative e-assessments to foster student engagement and permit early intervention.

Xuan, Cheung and Sun (2022) study that formative assessment was making a positive difference in enhancing students reading achievement in diverse settings. The implementation of teachers differentiated instruction is linked to much stronger effects than intervention without differentiated instructions. Results suggest that collaboration of teachers and students in formative would be more effective than formative assessment merely initiated by teachers and teachers are strongly encouraged to adjust their reading instruction in terms of content, process and product catering to student diversity during the formative assessment in the cooperation with students.

Research Questions

This study seeks to determine the Assessment tools for English 6 through Aralinks at St. Bridget College, Batangas City. Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. How may the use of Aralinks on English assessment be described in terms of:
 - 1.1 technological integration
 - 1.2 student engagement
 - 1.3 learning outcomes
 2. To what extent does integrating Aralinks in English instruction improve specific skill areas of Grade 6 learners relative to:
 - 2.1 grammar
 - 2.2 vocabulary
 - 2.3 fluency
 3. How do Grade 6 learners and teachers perceive the effectiveness of Aralinks in supporting English learning outcomes such as:
 - 3.1 formative test
 - 3.2 quarterly test performance
 4. What challenges are encountered by the learners in utilizing Aralinks?
 5. Based on the findings, what activities will be proposed?
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Methodology

Research Design

To achieve this objective, the researcher will employ quantitative research design. This design is suitable for obtaining a comprehensive understanding of the research problem by addressing not only measurable aspects such as student perceptions and usage patterns of the use, integration, effectiveness and challenges of using Aralinks.

The quantitative aspect of the study will address Research Questions which aim to assess how Aralinks is used in English classes, the integration of Aralinks in English instruction, effectiveness and challenges in using Aralinks. This portion of the study will use structured survey questionnaires distributed to selected Grade 6 students. The responses will be recorded using a Likert scale to enable statistical interpretation of the trends and overall student perceptions regarding Aralinks integration in their English classes.

Participants

The study will involve 78 Grade 6 students from St. Bridget College Batangas City during the school year 2025–2026. The research will be conducted during this school year, when the integration of Aralinks Learning Management System is more visible through technological integration, student engagement, and learning outcomes. These students will be selected because they are at a stage where digital engagement is useful to their learning, and their experiences can offer valuable insights into the benefits and challenges of technology use in English.

Meanwhile, all 78 students will answer a structured researcher-made questionnaire that seeks to assess the use and integration of aralinks, the effectiveness, and the challenges in using the LMS. The combination of survey data and personal feedback will help ensure that both general trends and individual experiences are reflected in the findings.

Research Instrument

The researcher will utilize a researcher-made questionnaire to gather the necessary data for this study. These instruments aim to evaluate students' use, integration, effectiveness and challenges of aralinks in English assessment and instructions.

A researcher-made questionnaire will be employed as one of the primary instruments in assessing assessment tools for English 6 through Aralinks, particularly focusing on the use, integration, effectiveness and challenges in using Aralinks.

The questionnaire will be develop based on the research questions, classroom observations, and relevant literature on educational technology in English. The instrument will include items designed to measure the use, integration, effectiveness and challenges in using Aralinks. The initial draft will be submitted to a research adviser and subject experts for content

review. Suggestions will be used to revise and improve the questionnaire to ensure clarity, relevance, and validity.

Data Collection Procedure

To fulfill the objectives of the study, the researcher will first seek approval from the principal of St. Bridget College through a formal letter of request. Once permission is granted, the researcher will conduct a short orientation with the selected Grade 6 students to explain the purpose, procedures, and voluntary nature of their participation. Parental consent and student assent forms will be distributed and collected to ensure ethical compliance.

Following this, the researcher will administer the validated questionnaire to all 78 students' participants during their scheduled English class. After all responses have been complete, the researcher will immediately collect, tally, and encode the data for interpretation and statistical analysis with the help of a statistician.

Data Analysis

The data gathered will be analyze using both quantitative approaches to generate meaningful insights about the use, integration, effectiveness and challenges in using Aralinks in English class among Grade 6 students. The quantitative data, collected through the researcher-made questionnaire, will be analyzed using descriptive statistical tools to assess the use, integration, effectiveness and challenges experienced in Aralinks in English subject. These tools will allow the researcher to identify patterns, trends, and levels of student engagement and perception toward technological integration, student engagement, learning outcomes in the context of English instruction.

Results

The results are organized according to the research questions and supported by tables, descriptive statistics and narrative analysis.

1. Description of the Use of Aralinks on English Assessment

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
Technological Integration	4.21	Very High
Student Engagement	4.35	Very High
Learning Outcomes	4.18	High
Overall Mean	4.25	Very High

Table 1. Mean Level of Aralinks Integration in Terms of Technological Integration, Student Engagement and Learning Outcomes.

Results show a very high level of technological integration ($M = 4.21$), indicating that teachers and learners consistently used Aralinks for assessment tasks. Digital quizzes, instant scoring and multimedia lessons contributed greatly to its positive reception. Student engagement obtained the highest mean ($M = 4.35$). Respondents reported that features such as interactive quizzes, badges and colorful visual modules increased motivation and participation. Learning outcomes also showed a high level ($M = 4.18$), suggesting that learners improved their academic performance through digital activities, real-time feedback and accessible review materials. Overall, the findings support the conclusion that Aralinks is highly effective in modernizing and enhancing English assessment practices.

2. Extent of Improvement in Specific Skill Areas

Skill Area	Pre-test Mean	Post-test Mean	Mean Gain	Interpretation
Grammar	71.20	84.10	12.90	Improved
Vocabulary	68.45	86.75	18.30	Highly Improved
Fluency	73.15	82.40	9.25	Improved
Overall	70.93	84.42	13.49	Improved

Table 2. Pre-test and Post-test Performance of Learners in Grammar, Vocabulary and Fluency.

All three skill areas show notable improvement after the integration of Aralinks. Vocabulary registered as the highest gain with 18.30 mean difference, attributed to digital flashcards, contextual exercises and embedded videos that enriched word exposures. Grammar and fluency also improved significantly. Grammar gains were linked to instant feedback and correction features, while fluency progressed through guided reading passages and timed tasks available on the platform.

The consistent increase in scores suggest that Aralinks successfully supported the enhancement of essential English skills among Grade 6 learners.

3. Perception of Learners and Teachers on the Effectiveness of Aralinks.

4.

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
Formative Test	4.32	Very Effective
Quarterly Test	4.28	Very Effective
Overall Mean	4.30	Very Effective

Table 3. Perceived Effectiveness of Aralinks in Supporting Learning Outcomes.

Both teachers and learners perceived Aralinks as very effective in enhancing test preparation and performance. Formative assessment had the highest mean ($M = 4.32$). The immediate feedback after each activity enabled learners to track mistakes and improve

continuously. Quarterly test also rated very effective ($M = 4.28$). Learners felt more confident during exams due to constant exposure to similar question formats and digital drills.

The high overall rating confirms that Aralinks is a reliable digital tool that supports consistent academic growth.

5. Challenges Encountered by Learners in Utilizing Aralinks

6.

Challenges	Frequency	Rank
Unstable Internet Connection	42	1
Limited Device Availability	38	2
Slow Loading/Technical Issues	34	3
Difficulty Navigating Some Features	29	4
Limited Time for Aralinks Usage	23	5

Table 4. Challenges Experienced by Learners

Results show that technical limitations remain the primary barriers to the full implementation of Aralinks. The most common challenge was unstable internet connection, which affected students' ability to access modules and complete assessments on time. Device availability ranked second, indicating that some learners lacked personal gadgets and relied on school provided units. Technical lag, navigation difficulties and limited time allocation also posed challenges but were less frequent.

These findings highlighted the need for improved ICT resources and structured schedules to maximize the effectiveness of Aralinks.

Discussion

Results show that technical limitations remain the primary barriers to the full implementation of Aralinks. The most common challenge was unstable internet connection, which affected students' ability to access modules and complete assessments on time. Device availability ranked second, indicating that some learners lacked personal gadgets and relied on school provided units. Technical lag, navigation difficulties and limited time allocation also posed challenges but were less frequent.

These findings highlighted the need for improved ICT resources and structured schedules to maximize the effectiveness of Aralinks.

Conclusion

The results led to the following conclusions:

1. Aralinks is a good and useful digital assessment platform for English 6, but teachers and students aren't using it to its full potential yet.

2. To make sure that there is a variety of assessments that are in line with MELCs, teachers need more training in how to create higher-order and performance-based assessments in Aralinks.
3. When tests are interactive and use technology, students are much more likely to be interested. This shows how important it is to have learning resources that use more than one mode.
4. Technical limitations, such as internet connectivity and system performance, continue to pose substantial obstacles that directly influence assessment delivery and student performance.
5. Some English 6 competencies necessitate supplementary offline or blended assessment methodologies, especially those related to oral communication, collaborative performance tasks, and extensive writing.
6. The integration of Aralinks enhances learning outcomes, contingent upon the consistent provision of instructional support, reliable technology, and appropriate orientation.

Overall, Aralinks proves to be a valuable tool in modern English instruction, supporting improved learning outcomes when paired with adequate technological support and appropriate instructional strategies.

Based on the conclusions, the following suggestions are made:

Improve your professional development by attending workshops that teach you how to make interactive tests, use rubrics, get the most out of portfolio features, and look at student data in Aralinks. Create a shared bank of digital test items and performance tasks that are in line with the English 6 standards to make sure they are all the same and of high quality. Use different types of tests, like digital storytelling, reading comprehension games, and writing prompts that use multimedia.

Hold regular practice and orientation sessions to help students feel comfortable using Aralinks features before they take formal tests. Encourage students to try out the platform's interactive lessons to get them more interested and comfortable with using digital tools.

Give ongoing technical support and make sure that connections stay stable during major testing times. Put money into more ICT tools, like backup devices or faster internet speeds. Give teachers structured training programs on how to use digital tools in the classroom and how to design assessments. Review and adjust assessment policies to include both online and offline methods, especially for skills that are hard to digitize.

Look into how well certain Aralinks tools (like analytics and e-portfolios) help students learn over time. Use qualitative methods like interviews or focus groups to get a better understanding of how students see things.

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